

SBI Life: Focus on Digital

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ABSTRACT

Focus on digital is a core strategy of SBI Life. The company has adopted two-pronged approach with reference to its digital initiatives - one, focus on IT infrastructure, and two, a compatible digital strategy. These initiatives have immensely contributed in terms of both improving the operational efficiency and business growth. At the same time, they have improved the key intangibles such as customer delight and employee engagement.

Keywords: *Digital, Customer satisfaction, customer delight, employee engagement*

INTRODUCTION

SBI Life is the life insurance arm of SBI. It was incorporated in 2000 and is registered with IRDAI since March 2001. The company is listed on the BSE and NSE. SBI Life strives to make insurance accessible to all, with its extensive presence across the country through its 947 offices, 17,464 employees, a large and productive individual agent network of about 170,096 agents, 57 corporate agents, a widespread bancassurance network of 14 partners, more than 28,000 partner branches, 107 brokers and other insurance marketing firms.

DIGITAL INITIATIVES

The company focuses on the digital initiatives with two-pronged approach – IT infrastructure and Digital Strategy.

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Figure 1: Digital Initiatives

Source: Investor Presentation, 2019

The company has embraced a two-dimensional procedure to augment the capability of its digitalization contributions.

1. Keep up scalable, efficient, and effective core systems and IT architecture.
2. Embrace a creative digital methodology that empowers unrivaled experience for customers, distributors, and employees by sending the instruments of Artificial Intelligence (AI), natural language processing (NLP), Robotic Process Automation (RPA) and analytics.

DIGITALIZATION APPROACH

The digitalization approach is tied-in with settling on insightful decisions to expand competitive advantage, growth, profit, and value.

- 1) Growth and profit: Digital interruption for the 'go to market strategy' focused on distributors.
- 2) Competitive Advantage: "Enriching client experience combined with risk mitigation measures" through digital.
- 3) Electronic report accommodation to facilitate the processing and limit the number of visits to offices.
- 4) Value: Digital enablers for employees pointed toward "managing internal customers aspirations" through digital.

IMPACT OF DIGITAL INITIATIVES

The impact of digital initiatives is felt across the board including: –

- 1) Employee engagement
- 2) Customer delight
- 3) Distributor Strength
- 4) Sustainable growth

Figure 2: Impact of Digital Initiatives

Source: Annual Report FY19

IMPACT ON CUSTOMER SERVICE

The key areas are queries resolved through chatbot, renewal premium collection through app, digital resolution of queries and requests and using WhatsApp to connect with customers.

Figure 3: Impact on Customer Service

Source: Annual Report FY19

IMPACT ON NEW BUSINESS ACQUISITION

The key areas include increase in proposals uploaded, increase in digitally sourced policies, easy upload of documents.

Figure 4: Impact on New Business Acquisition

Source: Annual Report FY19

CONCLUSION

Digital initiatives at SBI Digital are two pronged – one focused on IT infrastructure and second on a compatible digital strategy. The digital initiatives have benefited the company in terms of customer delight, acquiring new business and improving employee engagement. All in all, the digital initiatives have benefitted in terms of both the operating efficiency and growth.

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